

UNPACKING PAPERWORK OVERLOAD: IMPLICATIONS ON TEACHER HEALTH AND WELLNESS IN EAST-TACURONG DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

In an era of increasing demands on educators, paperwork overload has become a pressing issue that negatively impacts teacher health and well-being. This study utilized a phenomenology approach to explore the implications of paperwork overload on teachers in the East-Tacurong District during the 2024-2025 school year. Fifteen teachers from selected elementary and integrated schools in the district participated in interviews and focus group discussions. Thematic analysis of the data revealed that excessive administrative tasks—such as lesson planning, compliance documentation, student assessments, and professional development reporting—divert teachers' time and energy from instructional activities and student engagement. The findings highlight that paperwork overload contributes to psychological distress, physical exhaustion, emotional burnout, and work-life imbalance, which undermine teaching effectiveness and student engagement. While teachers employed coping strategies such as prioritization, delegation, overtime work, and digital tools, these solutions were often temporary and came at the cost of their health and well-being. Systematic changes are necessary to address these issues sustainably. Policy recommendations include streamlining documentation processes, implementing AI-driven digital documentation systems, and appointing administrative support staff to reduce teachers' clerical burdens. Schools should also provide professional development programs focused on time management and digital literacy to help teachers manage administrative tasks efficiently. Additionally, further research is needed to assess the long-term impact of paperwork reduction strategies on teaching performance and student learning outcomes. Addressing

paperwork overload is essential for fostering a enhances instructional quality. By implementing policy reforms and leveraging technology, educational institutions can help teachers focus on their primary role-educating and inspiring students-while mitigating the risk of burnout and ensuring a healthier, more effective teaching environment.

Keywords: *paperwork, teacher wellness*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

In an era characterized by increasing demands on educators, the issue of paperwork overload has emerged as a significant concern affecting teacher health and wellness. Given the pervasive nature of paperwork overload in the Philippine education system, there is an urgent need to examine its implications for teacher health and wellness. By examining the factors contributing to paperwork overload and its impact on teacher health, the study seeks to shed light on this pressing issue and propose strategies to mitigate its effects.

Internationally, research on teacher workload and its impact on well-being has gained traction in recent years. Studies have highlighted the detrimental effects of excessive paperwork on teacher stress, burnout, and job satisfaction (Chiang et al.,2018; Langton & Cook,2018). Furthermore, research has shown that high levels of paperwork can detract from instructional time, leading to decreased student learning outcomes (Klassen & Chiu,2011). Despite efforts to streamline administrative processes, many educators continue to struggle with paperwork overload, underscoring the need for further investigation into this issue. Despite the growing body of literature on teacher workload, there is a noticeable gap in research specifically examining paperwork overload and its implications for teacher health and wellness in the Philippine context. While studies from other countries provide valuable insights, the unique socio-cultural and organizational factors influencing teacher workload in the Philippines warrant dedicated investigation. Additionally, existing studies often focus on quantitative measures of workload, such as time spent on administrative tasks, overlooking the qualitative aspects of paperwork overload and its subjective impact on teacher well-being.

In the Philippine context, teachers face numerous challenges related to paperwork, including excessive reporting requirements, redundant documentation processes, and bureaucratic inefficiencies. These challenges are exacerbated by limited resources, inadequate support system, and the pressure to meet standardized performance targets. As a result, many educators experience heightened stress levels, decreased job satisfaction, and compromised mental health (Alonzo & Casanova,2019; De Asis & Cruz,2020). Also, Magonsik and Ngag (2025) stressed that teachers perceive the working conditions in DepEd as challenging, with high workloads, large class sizes, and limited resources.

By exploring the lived experiences of teachers in East Tacurong District, this study seeks to provide valuable insights into the underlying factors contributing to paperwork overload and its impact on teacher well-being. Ultimately, the findings of this study aim to inform policy and practice initiatives aimed at alleviating paperwork burden and promoting teacher health and wellness in the Philippines context.

Research Questions

This study aimed to unpack and explore the implications of paperwork overload for teacher well-being, focusing on the context of East-Tacurong District, during school year 2024-2025

Specifically, this delved with the following questions:

1. How do teachers in East-Tacurong District perceive the extent of paperwork overload in their daily work responsibilities?
2. What are the specific types of paperwork that contribute most significantly to teachers' workload in East-Tacurong District?
3. How do teachers in East-Tacurong District cope with paperwork overload, and what are the perceived effectiveness of these coping strategies on their health and well-being?
4. What are the perceived effects of paperwork overload on the psychological and physical health outcomes of teachers in East-Tacurong District?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, qualitative research, specifically the phenomenological approach, was employed to unpack and explore the implications of paperwork overload for teacher well-being, focusing on the context of east-Tacurong District, during school year 2024-2025.

Phenomenological research is a method that aims to delve into individuals' lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how they interpret these experiences. It operates under the assumption that individuals employ a universal structure or essence to derive meaning from their encounters. This research involves the interpretation of participants' emotions, perceptions, and beliefs to shed light on the fundamental essence of the phenomenon under investigation. An essential aspect of the phenomenological research design is the researcher's obligation to set aside any preconceived assumptions about the experience of phenomenon (Ho & Limpaecher, 2022).

Participants of the Study

Table 1 displays the participants' qualifications, as determined by the criteria established by the researcher before selecting eligible informants for the study. With a smaller number of cases, researchers can conduct a more in-depth and detailed analysis of each case. This allows for a richer exploration of the complexities, contexts, and unique characteristics of each participants of case, which is essential in qualitative research.

Hence, the study involved a total of 15 teachers in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria:

Table 1

Participants' Inclusion Criteria

Qualifications
<i>Participants: 15 Teachers</i>
The teacher-participants, must be: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Teacher in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025;2. Holding 3 and above designations;3. Holding multiple designations for 3 and above years; and4. Willing to participate in the in-depth interview and FGD.

Sampling Technique

During the conduct of this study, a Purposive Sampling Technique was intentionally utilized to carefully select the teachers in DepEd East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025, who meet the specific inclusion criteria established by the researcher.

Purposive sampling, alternately referred to as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, constitutes a variant of non-probability sampling. Within this approach, researcher exercise their own judgment and discretionary acumen in the selection of individuals from the population to partake in their survey endeavors (Alchemer, 2021).

Research Instruments

The researcher in this qualitative study used a semi-structured interview as an investigate instrument during both in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). Its purpose is to facilitate an in-depth exploration of the socio-emotional well-being of young learners as influenced by their exposure to different social media platforms in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the initial phase, the researcher diligently sought formal authorization from both the Superintendent of DepEd-Tacurong City and the Dean of the College of Graduate Studies (CGS). This authorization was essential to obtain the necessary permissions for the researcher to conduct the study, emphasizing the importance of ethical considerations.

Following this, a secondary authorization letter was sent to the District Supervisor, explicitly requesting access to the specific data required for this research. A meticulously crafted survey questionnaire was developed, subjected to rigorous evaluation, and then administered to the targeted participants.

The researcher employed a Purposive Sampling Technique to carefully select teachers as participants in this study. Assuming strict adherence to established health protocols, the researcher proceeded with conducting interviews and facilitating Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), all of which were conducted through face-to-face interactions.

Ultimately, the data collected from interviews and FGDs were systematically organized, subjected to comprehensive analysis, and interpreted using the thematic analysis approach. This approach was expected to provide a deeper understanding of the issues under investigation.

In the context of the study on the implications of paperwork overload for teacher well-being, focusing on the East-Tacurong District during the school year 2024-2025, a thematic analysis approach was used to examine the collected data. This methodology, as articulated in the study of Ngag and Ronquillo (2024) it involved systematically categorizing textual components such as statements, phrases, and words into organized groupings or categories. These categories were either derived from established frameworks or custom-developed to align with the study's specific objectives.

To execute this analytical process, a series of essential steps were diligently followed:

Initially, all data sources, including interview transcripts, notes from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), and relevant documents, were meticulously organized and prepared for analysis. This phase ensured the systematic arrangement and accessibility of the data.

Subsequently, the researchers deeply engaged with the data by conducting a thorough review of interview transcripts and FGD notes. This immersive process aided in gaining a comprehensive understanding of the content and context embedded within the collected information.

The third step involved initiating a systematic coding process. Initial codes were generated by identifying meaningful segments or patterns within the data, capturing essential concepts, ideas, or themes related to paperwork overload and its implications for teacher well-being.

Following coding, the identified codes were grouped into preliminary themes based on shared meaning or relevance. This step aimed to establish an initial structure for organizing the data and exploring the implications of paperwork overload for teacher well-being in the East-Tacurong District during the school year 2024-2025.

Next, the emerging themes and their corresponding codes underwent a process of review and refinement. Researchers ensured the consistency and clarity of these themes, making necessary adjustments as they interpreted the data within the context of the study.

Relevant data excerpts, such as quotes or segments extracted from interviews and FGDs, were selected and associated with the respective themes. These excerpts served as supporting evidence for the identified themes, enhancing the credibility and depth of the analysis.

Finally, the thematic analysis extended beyond surface-level identification. Researchers interpreted the meaning and implications of each theme within the context of the study's objectives. They sought patterns, connections, and variations within the themes to provide a comprehensive understanding of the implications of paperwork overload for teacher well-being in the East-Tacurong District during the school year 2024-2025.

This meticulous and structured process of thematic analysis enabled researchers to systematically explore and comprehend the socio-emotional impacts of paperwork overload on teachers in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat.

Scope and Limitations

This study investigated the impact of paperwork overload on the health and wellness of teachers in the East-Tacurong District. It examined various sources of paperwork that teachers in East-Tacurong District encountered regularly, such as administrative forms, grading sheets, lesson plans, and reports.

The study was limited to teachers within the East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat. Findings were not generalizable to other districts or regions. The study specifically focused on paperwork-related factors affecting teacher health and wellness. Other stressors or factors impacting teacher well-being were not extensively explored. The study involved a specific number of teachers from selected schools within East-Tacurong District, which may have limited the breadth of perspectives and experiences represented.

By delineating these boundaries, the study aimed to provide a focused examination of paperwork overload and its implications on teacher health and wellness within the specific educational context of East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In an era characterized by increasing demands on educators, the issue of paperwork overload has emerged as a significant concern affecting teacher health and wellness. In this study, qualitative research, specifically the phenomenological approach, was employed to unpack and explore the implications of paperwork overload for teacher well-being, focusing on the context of East -Tacurong District, during school year 2024-2025. The study involved a total of 15 teachers in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria. This research was conducted within carefully selected elementary and integrated schools in East-Tacurong District, City Schools` Division of Tacurong City. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the gathered data from interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD).

The findings from East-Tacurong District mirror broader concerns in the education sector regarding paperwork overload. The excessive time spent on administrative tasks negatively impacts teaching effectiveness, student engagement, and teacher well-being. Research highlights the need for policy interventions to reduce unnecessary documentation requirements and promote efficient administrative processes.

Further, the findings from East-Tacurong District echo broader research on teacher workload, emphasizing the significant impact of paperwork on teaching effectiveness, well-being, and student engagement. Lesson planning, compliance documentation, student assessment, extra-curricular paperwork, and professional development reporting all contribute to teachers' administrative burdens. While these tasks serve important functions in education, excessive paperwork diverts teachers' attention away from instruction and student interaction. To alleviate this challenge, policymakers and school administrators should consider streamlining documentation processes, reducing redundant paperwork, and implementing digital solutions that simplify administrative tasks. By addressing these concerns, teachers can dedicate more time to their primary role—educating and inspiring students.

Furthermore, the various strategies teachers use to manage paperwork overload, including prioritization, delegation, technology use, emotional resilience, overtime work, and calls for policy improvements. While these coping mechanisms offer temporary relief, many have negative consequences, particularly on teachers' health and work-life balance. The literature supports these findings, emphasizing that while individual strategies can mitigate stress, systemic changes are necessary to create sustainable solutions. Addressing paperwork overload through institutional support, policy reforms, and technological advancements will be essential in ensuring that teachers can focus on their primary role—educating and nurturing students.

Finally, the findings from East-Tacurong District highlight the severe impact of paperwork overload on teachers' psychological and physical health. The themes of psychological distress, physical exhaustion, reduced teaching effectiveness, emotional burnout, and work-life imbalance align with recent literature demonstrating that excessive

administrative demands undermine teachers' well-being and professional effectiveness. Research supports the participants' concerns, emphasizing that stress, anxiety, fatigue, and burnout are prevalent among teachers facing high workloads. Addressing paperwork overload through policy changes, digital solutions, and workload reduction strategies is crucial to ensuring that teachers can focus on their core mission—educating and inspiring students. By prioritizing teacher well-being, educational institutions can foster a healthier, more sustainable teaching environment that benefits both educators and learners.

Conclusions

The following inferences were made in light of this study's findings:

1. The study underscores the detrimental impact of paperwork overload on teachers in East-Tacurong District, mirroring global concerns about excessive administrative tasks. The resulting psychological distress, physical exhaustion, and diminished teaching effectiveness call for urgent policy interventions to reduce unnecessary documentation and streamline administrative processes.
2. Excessive paperwork not only affects teachers' well-being but also compromises student engagement and instructional quality. Research highlights the need for systemic reforms, including digital solutions and reduced bureaucratic demands, to allow teachers to focus more on meaningful classroom interactions.
3. While teachers employ coping strategies such as prioritization, delegation, and overtime work, these often come at the expense of their health and work-life balance. Sustainable solutions require institutional support, policy reforms, and technological advancements to minimize administrative burdens effectively.
4. Addressing paperwork overload is crucial in fostering a sustainable teaching environment. By implementing workload reduction strategies and prioritizing teacher well-being, educational institutions can enhance teaching effectiveness, prevent burnout, and ultimately improve student learning outcomes.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings, the following were recommended:

1. DepEd may implement a **centralized digital documentation system** that reduces redundant paperwork and automates administrative processes. By integrating AI-driven tools and standardized digital templates, teachers can efficiently complete necessary documentation with minimal time investment, allowing them to focus more on instructional activities.
2. Schools may **restructure administrative workloads** by appointing **dedicated administrative support staff** or assigning specific clerical responsibilities to non-teaching personnel. This initiative will significantly reduce the burden on teachers,

ensuring that their primary focus remains on student learning and classroom engagement.

3. Teachers can **maximize available digital tools** such as automated grading systems, lesson plan templates, and voice-to-text documentation software to streamline paperwork. Professional development programs on **time management and digital literacy** should also be provided to help teachers efficiently handle administrative tasks without compromising their well-being.

4. Further studies may explore the **long-term effects of paperwork reduction strategies** on teacher performance and student learning outcomes. Researchers should also investigate **innovative policy reforms** and best practices from other educational systems to provide data-driven recommendations for optimizing teacher workloads.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In preparation for conducting the study on the implications of paperwork overload for teacher well-being, focusing on the context of East-Tacurong District during the school year 2024-2025, all proposed plans and recommendations were formally presented to East-West Mindanao Colleges Inc. to ensure adherence to prescribed procedures and protocols (Cerdana, and Ngag, 2024). Within the context of this research, which focused on exploring paperwork overload for teacher well-being, it was crucial to emphasize the paramount importance of ethical considerations.

Prior to commencing this study during the school year 2024-2025, the following ethical principles were meticulously observed:

Informed Consent: Explicit and informed consent was diligently obtained from all parents or guardians of participating students. They were fully informed about the study's objectives, methodologies, potential risks, and benefits. Participation was voluntary, and participants had the autonomy to withdraw at any time without consequences (Ngag, 2023).

Anonymity and Confidentiality: To protect the identities and responses of participants, stringent measures were implemented to maintain anonymity and confidentiality. Pseudonyms or codes were used instead of actual names, and all collected data was securely stored with limited access restricted to the research team.

Avoiding Harm: Sensitive topics related to socio-emotional well-being and social media exposure were handled with careful consideration for potential emotional and psychological impacts on participants. Strategies were in place to minimize distress, and support services were readily accessible as needed.

Researcher-Participant Relationship: The researcher maintained a professional and respectful relationship with all participants, ensuring their dignity and well-being

throughout the research process. Actions that could exploit or harm participants were strictly avoided (Ngag, and Dolutan, 2024).

Data Protection: Stringent adherence to data protection regulations was upheld to safeguard all personal information collected during the study. Secure storage and transmission protocols were implemented to prevent unauthorized access.

Voluntary Participation: Participants were assured that their involvement in the study was voluntary and free from coercion or external pressure.

Researcher Bias: The researcher remained vigilant against biases that could influence data collection and analysis, promoting objectivity and transparency in reporting findings.

Institutional Approval: Ethical clearance was sought from relevant institutional review boards or ethics committees prior to initiating the study.

Honesty and Integrity: Research findings were reported truthfully and accurately, without manipulation or distortion, to uphold the integrity of the study.

Beneficence: Potential benefits of the research to educational practices and policies were carefully considered, aiming to contribute positively to the enhancement of the education system.

Cultural Sensitivity: The researcher demonstrated cultural sensitivity by respecting local customs, beliefs, and practices within the research setting, avoiding the imposition of external values on participants.

Inclusion and Diversity: The study prioritized inclusivity and diversity in participant selection, aiming to encompass a broad spectrum of teachers' struggles in East-Tacurong District.

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REFERENCES

- Alchemer. (2021). Survey Sampling Methods. Retrieved from <https://www.alchemer.com>
- Alonzo, G. P., & Casanova, L. B. (2019). Job Satisfaction and Stress of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Tacurong City. *International Journal of Research-Granthaalayah*, 7(2), 102-110.
- Bakker, A. B., & de Vries, J. D. (2022). Job demands–resources theory and work engagement: The role of teachers' workload and well-being. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 118, 103780.
- Cerdana, CC, & Ngag, JBJU (2024). IMPLEMENTATION OF TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION (TLE) PROGRAM IN TACURONG CITY DIVISION: ITS IMPACT ON THE HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' CAREER PREPAREDNESS. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2 (8), 735–746. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13292709>
- Chiang, Y. T., Hsu, C. H., Chen, S. Y., Chen, S. J., & Lin, C. J. (2018). The Effect of Workload on Job Stress, Burnout, and Job Satisfaction among Hospital Foodservice Workers. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(6), 1119

- De Asis, G. V., & Cruz, C. R. (2020). Working conditions and work stress of public school teachers: basis for employee welfare program development. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(2), 582-586
- Dolutan, M. N., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2024). LIVED EXPERIENCES OF CENTENNIAL TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL MODERNIZATION: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL ANALYSIS IN DEPED BAGUMBAYAN DISTRICT III. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(7), 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.17613/n5qw-6920>
- Ho, L., & Limpaecher, A. (2022, March 17). What is phenomenological research design? *De/ve*. <https://delvetool.com/blog/phenomenology>
- Langton, R. R., & Cook, A. (2018). Paperwork overload: A social work dilemma. *Social Work Education*, 37(3), 337-349.
- Magonisik, R. W., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2025). UNVEILING TEACHERS` MOTIVATION OF LEAVING DEPED TO TEACH ABROAD: A NARRATIVE INQUIRY. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(2), 791–806. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14948796>
- Ngag, J.B. (2023). Unveiling The Literary Appreciation of Teduray Students: A Case Study Analysis of Their Works. *Boletin De Literatura Oral - Tradition Oral Literature*, 10(1), 30-3. <http://boletindeliteratuoral.com/index.php/bdlo/article/view/5>
- Ngag, J.B. (2023). Efficacy of Téduray Literature Module in Teaching English. *CEMJP*, 31(1), 404–409. <https://doi.org/10.57030/23364890.cemj.31.1.3>
- Ronquillo, K. C., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2024). OVERCOMING LINGUISTIC HURDLES: INVESTIGATING CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY MAGUINDANAON STUDENTS IN ACHIEVING PROFICIENCY IN SPEAKING ENGLISH. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(7), 1069–1081. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13133747>